
ADVANCING OPEN RESEARCH IN AFRICA

UNDERSTANDING THE POLITICAL ECONOMY
OF REFORM

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study uses a political economy approach to examine how Open Research is understood, who holds influence over reform, and which political and institutional dynamics shape opportunities for advancing Open Research in African research systems. The analysis aims to identify priority stakeholders, policy entry points, and strategic considerations to guide future initiatives and programmes. The study combines a targeted desk review of policy and academic literature with semi-structured interviews with stakeholders from funders, international organisations, research institutions, and policy communities.

Five Dynamics Shaping Open Research Reform

Convergence and variation in interpretations of Open Research

Global narratives emphasise openness, and efficiency. African policy frameworks focus on sovereignty, equity and system strengthening. Convergence around “governed openness”.

Layered ecosystem of power and influence

Multilaterals shape global norms. Philanthropics influence behaviour. National governments strongest formal authority. SGCs play important bridging role.

Institutional windows for system change

Opportunities for embedding Open Research within existing processes, reporting cycles, national STI strategies and science diplomacy platforms. Operationally - grant conditions and research assessment are entry points.

Structural barriers to prioritisation and reform

Lack of high-level prioritisation, fragmented policy environment, sustainable financing, regulatory uncertainty, entrenched academic reward system and commercial publishing dominance.

Framing and narrative competition in policy debates

Traction when reform linked to economic competitiveness, innovation, integrity or public accountability. In Africa, connect to sovereignty and equitable global knowledge systems.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Five Priorities for Driving System Change

Priority stakeholders and coalition-building

Prioritise those with decision-making authority, STI and finance ministries, parliamentary committees and SGCs. Focus advocacy on institutions who can adopt policy reforms. Anchor engagement with African Union and other regional frameworks and commitments.

Institutional and policy entry points for influence

Embed reform within structured policy processes such as UNESCO reporting cycles, African Union policy reviews, and national STI strategy revisions. Funding and research assessment reforms are actionable entry points for influencing researcher behaviour.

Incentives, infrastructure, and governance design

Reform research assessment systems. Strengthen repositories and interoperability standards. Establish governance frameworks for responsible data sharing. Build institutional capacity, including specialised roles for data stewardship and research infrastructure management

Strategic framing and political positioning

Align narratives with institutional priorities. Economic competitiveness, innovation, and public accountability narratives may resonate with finance and development ministries. Research integrity and enhancing collaboration may engage research communities and research funders.

Learning questions for adaptive strategy

Reform processes are political and context-specific, initiatives should use an adaptive approach to programming. Key questions: Where is political momentum emerging? Are reforms translating into practice? Which coalitions lead to policy adoption? Is Open Research is becoming embedded within broader agendas?

Acronyms

AfCFTA	African Continental Free Trade Area
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOSP	African Open Science Platform
APC	Article processing charges
ASREN	Arab States Research and Education Network
AU	African Union
AUDA-NEPAD	African Union Development Agency–New Partnership for Africa’s Development
EAC	East African Community
EASTECO	East African Science and Technology Commission
FCDO	Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office (UK)
GDN	Global Development Network
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
LIBSENSE	Library Support for Embedded NREN Services and E-infrastructure
LMICs	Low- and Middle-Income Countries
NREN	National Research and Education Network(s)
PEA	Political Economy Analysis
PLOS	Public Library of Science
R&D	Research and Development
RECs	Regional Economic Communities
REN	Research and Education Network(s)
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SGCs	Science Granting Councils
SGCI Africa	Science Granting Councils Initiative
STI	Science, Technology and Innovation
STISA 2034	Science, Technology and Innovation Strategy for Africa 2034
TCC	Training Centre in Communication
TWGs	Technical Working Groups
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WACREN	West and Central African Research and Education Network

Introduction

Achieving meaningful progress towards Open Research[1] reform requires a clear understanding of the opportunities and barriers shaping adoption within the current system, the levers for change that exist across different institutional settings, and the actors who hold influence over reform processes. This study uses a political economy approach and stakeholder mapping to understand how Open Research policy can be advanced at global and regional levels, with a particular emphasis on Africa.

The analysis seeks to identify the key individuals, organisations, and networks operating in the research policy space, assess their levels of interest and influence in advancing Open Research, and examine the political, economic, and institutional factors that enable or constrain reform. The findings will support those seeking to advance Open Research by informing influencing strategies, guiding engagement in science diplomacy spaces, and shaping programme design and implementation.

What is Open Research/Open Science?

Open Science – or Open Research – represents a fundamental transformation of the research system, making scientific knowledge – publications, protocols, data, code – freely available, accessible, and reusable and the research process open, collaborative, and transparent. Open Science is science that is open to society, by valuing indigenous and alternative knowledge and engaging communities, policymakers and practitioners in its generation, curation and application.

Key analytical questions

- 1. How is Open Research understood, framed, and prioritised by different actors, particularly those based in or working with African research systems?** How do narratives, definitions, and framings of Open Research differ across different stakeholders, and how do these framings shape policy preferences, funding priorities, and approaches to reform?
- 2. Who are the key actors influencing Open Research policy and practice, and how are power, interests, and incentives distributed across the research ecosystem?** Which individuals, organisations, and networks hold influence over agenda-setting and decision-making at global and African regional levels, and how do formal institutions, informal norms, and relationships shape their ability to enable or constrain reform?
- 3. Which policy spaces, funding mechanisms, and science diplomacy arenas offer leverage for advancing system-level change in support of Open Research in Africa?** Where do windows of opportunity exist for influencing reform, including through development cooperation, multilateral processes, and regional African initiatives, and which actors are positioned to act as change agents or coalition builders?

1. This report uses the term Open Research but this is often used interchangeably with the term Open Science. We preserve Open Science if that is the term used by interviewees or quoted documents.

- 4. What political, economic, and institutional factors constrain the prioritisation of Open Research at high levels of policymaking and system reform, particularly in African contexts?** How do incentive structures, financing models, regulatory environments, and global power asymmetries limit political attention, reduce reform ambition, or impede sustained system-level transformation?
- 5. What role do narratives and framing play in shaping opportunities for Open Research reform?** Which discursive approaches seem to gain attention or legitimacy in different contexts, and how might they affect alignment with policy priorities, funding agendas, and coalition-building efforts in African settings?

Methodology

Desk review

The study draws on a targeted desk review of relevant documents to establish the analytical context and inform subsequent data collection. Sources reviewed included:

- Project documentation and outputs produced under the INASP led and FCDO funded Strengthening Science Diplomacy and Official Development Assistance Policy for Research Publishing Reform project.
- Peer-reviewed academic articles and books on Open Research and Open Science
- Policy and technical documents produced by international organisations and global initiatives active in this field.

The desk review focused on identifying key actors, dominant narratives, policy debates, and political economy dynamics shaping Open Research reform, with particular attention to Africa and the Global South (see References).

Key informant interviews

The primary empirical component of the study consisted of 10 semi-structured key informant interviews (KIIs) with 11 interviewees operating at different levels of the Open Research ecosystem. Informants included representatives of research funders, international organisations, policy makers, African research institutes, civil society organisations and networks, and firms advancing Open Research and Open Science initiatives in the Global South. Interviews explored informants' perspectives on Open Research priorities, incentives and constraints, power dynamics, and opportunities for system-level change. Interview data were analysed thematically, with attention to converging and diverging views across stakeholder groups and regions. The identity and organisation of participants has been kept anonymous.

Limitations

While informed by political economy analysis concepts and stakeholder mapping perspectives, this study was not designed as a formal political economy analysis or stakeholder mapping exercise following a specific methodological framework. Rather, it should be understood as a landscape analysis with a focused examination of actors, interests, and political economy dynamics relevant to Open Research reform. The analysis could be strengthened through engagement with additional informants, including actors who could not be interviewed within the timeframe of this phase, and through deeper exploration of specific country or institutional contexts in future work.

Five Dynamics Shaping Open Research Reform

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1. Convergence and variation in interpretations of Open Research

The analysis reveals broad convergence around the meaning of Open Research (or Open Science), alongside important differences in emphasis, sequencing, and political interpretation. Across sources, Open Research is framed as systemic and lifecycle-wide; as governed through policy frameworks rather than an absolute principle; as closely linked to questions of sovereignty and state capability in African policy contexts; and as a vehicle for equity and system-strengthening, albeit one marked by persistent implementation tensions.

Systemic scope and terminological fragmentation

Across sources, Open Research is consistently framed as a **broad, systemic, and normative approach** to the production, governance, and use of knowledge, rather than a narrow set of technical practices such as open access or data sharing. There is convergence around its **lifecycle scope** (encompassing questions, methods, data, software, and partnerships) and the view that it is “more about the research process than the research outputs” (interviewee), implying shifts in infrastructures, incentives, and science–society relationships. At the same time, interviewees emphasized persistent terminological fragmentation and lack of shared language: “There is no homogeneous language... different conversations are being labelled with different names” (interviewee).

At the global level, the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science provides the most authoritative articulation, defining openness as “an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone” (UNESCO, 2021, p.7), while also opening research processes and evaluation to actors beyond the traditional scientific community. This framing is widely echoed by multilateral organisations and major funders, which position Open Research as a normative **global public good** centred on harmonisation, shared principles, and systemic reform of research assessment, infrastructure, and incentives.

At the continental level, the African Union (AU) Science Technology and Innovation Strategy (STISA 2034) explicitly positions **open science as part of Africa’s STI transformation agenda**, noting the “universal movement towards open science” (AU, p.5) and calling for action to “accelerate the transition to open science across the continent” (AU, p.16).

A recurring **tension emerges between expansive definitions and practical entry points**. Although Open Research is described as lifecycle-wide, some actors, particularly funders and publishers, continue to approach it primarily through open access and publishing costs, only later extending to data, software, and infrastructure. This reflects a gap between systemic ambition and incentive structures that still privilege end products over open processes. While open access remains politically salient, interviews suggest it is increasingly seen as only a partial entry point into a broader reform agenda that also includes collaboration models, infrastructure, and research assessment reform.

Despite agreement on scope, interviews reveal persistent ambiguity and fear around what “open” entails: “There is still a lot of kind of misunderstanding around open research and a lot of fear around the more general term of open... More work needs to be done to understand the nuances” (interviewee). Concerns centre on releasing data without safeguards or losing control over sensitive knowledge[2].

2. These concerns resonate with debates on research security, which refers to policies and practices aimed at protecting research systems from misuse, unauthorized knowledge transfer, or uncontrolled access to sensitive data and technologies, particularly in international collaboration. Although interviewees did not explicitly use this term, the risks they describe reflect issues commonly addressed in research security frameworks (OECD, 2022).

While not confined to the Global South, these fears are described as more acute where regulatory capacity and legal clarity are weaker, shaping reform preferences toward gradual, safeguard-heavy approaches, in contrast to more standardised compliance models adopted by some global funders.

Governed openness: safeguards, standards, and regulation

A consistent point of convergence is the **rejection of unconditional openness**. Rather than promoting openness as an absolute good, **Open Research is framed as governed and contextual**, requiring judgement about what can be shared, when, and under which conditions. The UNESCO Recommendation is explicit that restrictions may be legitimate when linked to human rights, privacy, confidentiality, national security, or the protection of indigenous and local knowledge.

This **“governed openness”** framing is echoed in African Union data governance discussions, which emphasise “open data, interoperability standards and data-sharing initiatives” alongside “safeguards that protect people from the harm of data misuse” to ensure “safe use and reuse of data” (AU, 2022, p.7). Openness is thus framed as standards-based and trust-enabled, supporting differentiated implementation rather than one-size-fits-all mandates. In practice, the challenge is often not open versus closed, but how to sequence and align openness and protection within research, innovation, and policy processes.

This framing places Open Research within broader societal concerns, including declining trust in science, misinformation, and the commercialisation and enclosure of knowledge. It positions openness not only as a matter of efficiency or equity, but as a way of **reasserting science as a public good**, governed in the public interest and responsive to societal needs, often linked to calls for transparency standards, open infrastructures, and reform of publishing markets.

Sovereignty, data as strategic asset, and state capability

Compared to global narratives centred on access and transparency, African policy frameworks frame Open Research as a matter of **sovereignty and strategic choice**, often summarised as “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”. African Union-aligned instruments present **data as both a public good and a strategic asset**, emphasising national and regional capacity to govern and derive value from it. In this view, openness is not solely a technical standard but a policy and governance challenge shaped by national priorities and historical asymmetries: “Openness is not only a technical problem to be solved but is also a social, cultural, and moral issue” (Levin & Leonelli in Chiware & Skelly, 2022, p.8).

As the African Union Data Policy Framework states, “Data is increasingly recognised as a strategic asset, integral to policy-making, private and public sector innovation and performance management, and creating new entrepreneurial opportunities for businesses and individuals” (2022, 18). The framework further calls for moving “beyond only negative compliance regulation to positive enabling regulation” (AU, 2022, 8), framing openness not just as access, but as a matter of state capability and institutions able to regulate “agilely” and create trusted conditions for sharing.

Equity and capacity-strengthening

Another area of convergence is the framing of Open Research as a capacity-and systems-strengthening strategy rather than primarily an access agenda. While global narratives emphasise efficiency, transparency, and reproducibility, Global South-focused sources stress its role in **addressing structural asymmetries in global science**, enhancing the visibility, relevance, and usability of locally produced research and enabling more equitable participation in agenda-setting and collaboration.

This shift appears clearly in interviews, where equity is a dominant lens, covering affordability of publishing, access to evidence for policy, and recognition of Global South institutions as knowledge producers rather than consumers: “Open research really speaks to collaborative research... multidisciplinary... where people can share ideas and look within their various countries” (interviewee). Equity thus operates both as a moral narrative and a strategic policy demand, informing debates on funding models, regional platforms, and incentive reform.

In summary, there is broad rhetorical convergence around Open Research as systemic, inclusive, and equity-oriented, but clear differences in emphasis and sequencing. Global institutions tend to foreground policy alignment, transparency, and reform of publishing and assessment systems, while African policy actors place stronger weight on sovereignty, capacity-strengthening, infrastructure development, and equitable participation in global knowledge production. These distinctions are not merely discursive; they ultimately shape policy preferences, funding priorities, and reform trajectories.

2. Layered ecosystem of power and influence

Across documents and interviews, Open Research appears as a multi-level, politically layered ecosystem in which influence over agenda-setting and implementation is unevenly distributed. Although often framed as a collective reform effort, authority and incentives are shaped by formal mandates, funding flows, infrastructure control, and market power. A distinction emerges between actors with formal decision authority and those with convening or technical influence. At the same time, a recurring paradox is noted: despite governments holding formal power, **Open Research is not widely treated as a high-level political priority**, limiting sustained mobilisation.

Global norm and agenda-setters

At the global level, the UN system links Open Research to broader development agendas such as the SDGs, embedding it within global development legitimacy. UNESCO is consistently identified as the primary norm-setter, with its Recommendation on Open Science defining the global reference framework for governments: “At the UN level, UNESCO has tended to be the closest there is to a kind of global fora for setting a direction of travel” (interviewee). Its influence is largely normative and convening, shaping discourse, peer learning, and reporting frameworks, rather than coercive, as interviews emphasise that **multilateral bodies influence agenda-setting more than implementation**.

Alongside UNESCO, large philanthropic funders such as the Gates Foundation and the Wellcome Trust are frequently identified as influential agenda drivers through funding conditions, open access mandates, and infrastructure investments. Their leverage stems from financial power over grantees and publishing markets. However, interviews note a constraint: “Their bigger success is the convening power while their weakness is taking action: philanthropies are reluctant to promote policies that may affect their grantees” (interviewee). This points to a political economy **tension between signalling reform and enforcing measures** that might disrupt existing research ecosystems.

National governments and science and ICT ministries: formal authority

National governments, science ministries, and legislatures emerge as the most powerful formal actors in enabling systemic change. They shape legislation, incentives, and funding, and therefore the “enabling policy environment” within which Open Research can advance or stall. As one interviewee put it, “The default influencer here is going to be legislators; you can only create an enabling policy environment in legislation”. Another stressed the **ministerial entry point**: “We get our guidance from the Science and Education Ministers... Those ministries are the entry points”. Without **ministerial and legislative backing**, Open Research remains fragmented and voluntary.

This **emphasis on public authority** is reinforced at the global normative level. The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science explicitly states that “the public sector has a leading role to play in the implementation of open science” (UNESCO, 2021, p.16). Documentary sources reinforce this, noting that “National and institutional policy frameworks, regulations or legislation on data sharing, access, and use are all necessary steps in enabling open science” (Chiwere & Skelly, 2022, p.4).

In African contexts, this is reinforced by regional frameworks under the African Union Commission and the African Union Development Agency (AUDA-NEPAD), which coordinate continental strategies such as STISA 2034: “The African Heads of State and Government (AU Assembly) has the authority to demonstrate the collective political will of the African continent to prioritise STI for development” (STISA 2034, p.19). The African Union Data Policy Framework explicitly calls on Member States to “establish an open data policy which sets open standards for the production and processing of data” (2022, p.52). African Union data policy underscores that implementation spans science, ICT, and data governance portfolios. At the sub-regional level, bodies such as the East African Science and Technology Commission (EASTECO) play a harmonising role across borders, for example through the East African Regional STI Policy: “The inclusion of Open Science principles and guidelines in the East African Regional Science, Technology and Innovation Policy marks a first for the region and Africa” (EAC, 2024), functioning as “strategic compasses” that encourage peer influence across states.

Science Granting Councils as emerging power centres

Documents and interviews identify the Science Granting Councils (SGCs), particularly the Science Granting Councils Initiative (SGCI), as a promising African-led entry point. Positioned at the **intersection of funding, incentives, and national research priorities**, SGCs have practical leverage over research behaviour. Unlike global funders, they are embedded in domestic political systems, making them key mediators between international norms and national priorities and positioning them to play a stronger role in shaping national and regional STI policy agendas. This role is reflected in SGCI phase three Outcome 2, which seeks to strengthen the policy influence of African SGCs through enhanced monitoring, evaluation and learning capacity, evidence-informed policy engagement, and participation in national, regional, and international STI policy dialogues.

Regional infrastructure and connectivity actors

Open Research in practice depends on digital infrastructure. Yet **many countries lack national research infrastructure roadmaps** to prioritise investments, coordinate infrastructure development, and guide long-term capacity building. Examples such as South Africa’s Research Infrastructure Roadmap illustrate how strategic planning can support more coherent ecosystem development and may offer lessons for other countries in the region.

Within this landscape, **Regional Research and Education Networks** (RENs), including UbuntuNet Alliance, the West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN), and the Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN), are identified as **pivotal operational actors**: “National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) provide excellent platforms for aggregating broadband connectivity” (AU, 2022, p.41). They hold significant technical and infrastructural power, particularly where connectivity costs are binding constraints, even if their influence is less visible in global discourse.

STISA 2034 reinforces **shared infrastructure as a continental strategy**, noting that “intra-Africa partnerships are critical for exploiting economies of scale” (p.16), including shared R&D infrastructure, and warning that the scarcity of such partnerships “undermines the continent’s ability to develop large-scale research and innovation initiatives” (p.16) as well as bilateral country collaborations on specific R&I initiatives. The African Union Data Policy Framework recommendations similarly emphasise prioritising “data partnerships (including options like databanks)...as mechanisms for advancing quality and privacy-preserving open data” (2022, p.52).

Coalitions, intermediaries, and knowledge networks

Documents and interviews emphasise that Open Research cannot be implemented by governments alone. **Research organisations, libraries, data stewards, and research communities are essential operational actors** across the full research cycle. Intermediary organisations and networks, such as the African Open Science Platform (AOSP), the Library Support for Embedded NREN Services and E-infrastructure (LIBSENSE), the Global Development Network (GDN), or INASP, lack formal legislative authority but shape coordination, capacity-strengthening, and policy diffusion: “Their role can be to connect national level efforts at the regional and global level” (interviewee). Their influence is relational and convening, bridging fragmented ecosystems and translating norms into practice. Cross-sectoral partnerships, including collaborations between Training Centre in Communication (TCC Africa), Public Library of Science (PLOS), and EASTECO, illustrate how coalitions can facilitate high-level dialogue and accelerate norm diffusion.

The market power of commercial publishers and tech “hyperscalers”

Private sector actors and **major commercial publishers and technology firms** such as Google and Microsoft are seen as highly influential due to their **control over platforms, data, and analytics**. Their power is economic and infrastructural, and their business models may conflict with the public-good orientation of Open Research, particularly on data governance and access. African Union data governance language reflects this tension, calling for “trust mechanisms to support data sharing under terms and conditions agreed upon by all parties” (AU, 2022, p.9), including liability issues such as data accuracy. This underscores a key policy arena: who defines the conditions of reuse, responsibility, and benefit-sharing across public and private platforms.

In summary, Open Research is shaped by a layered distribution of power: governments and regional bodies hold formal authority; funders exert financial leverage; Research and Education Networks and technology firms control key infrastructure; and intermediary coalitions wield relational influence. Although public leadership is normatively affirmed, Open Research remains unevenly prioritised at high political levels. Reform trajectories are shaped by the interaction of mandates, funding incentives, infrastructure control, and market interests.

3. Institutional windows for system change

Across documents and interviews, the main opportunities for advancing system-level change in Open Research in Africa lie in **translating global commitments into national implementation**, aligning openness with politically salient agendas, leveraging science diplomacy arenas, and reforming incentive structures. While normative convergence is strong, progress depends on identifying concrete policy spaces and actors able to operationalise reform.

From global principles to national implementation

The most consistently cited opportunity is the **shift from global norm-setting to domestic institutionalisation**. The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science is described as a political anchor, particularly because Member States must report on implementation. As one interviewee observed: “The moments ministries realize they are the main agency responsible for reporting to UNESCO about these issues creates an obligation”. These reporting cycles create recurring “policy windows” for legislative reform, regulatory adjustment, and funding rule changes, establishing structured accountability moments within ministries.

There is broad agreement that **national ministries and SGCs** are the most actionable entry points, given their control over funding and research assessment. Several interviewees emphasised institutionalising engagement with lawmakers rather than relying solely on executive ministries or ad hoc consultations. Parliamentary forums can serve as agenda-setting spaces and cross-party platforms that sustain reform beyond individual projects. As one interviewee noted, legislative change requires coalitions able to translate technical proposals into policy language: “The primary focus has to be coalitions that can talk to policy makers, that understand how to amend legislation” (interviewee). One proposal was to **embed Open Research in formal parliamentary structures**: “Set up a parliamentary working group that engages continuously with legislators... it works very well in many other areas”. Such mechanisms could also create a foundation for regional or continental coordination, for example by linking national parliamentary engagement with African Union-level policy dialogue or technical working groups to align priorities and share emerging legislative practices.

Development planning and cross-sector policy integration

A second opportunity lies in embedding Open Research within national and continental development planning. Open Science is referenced in STI, digital transformation, and sustainable development strategies, with the Communiqué on Open Science stating that “Open science removes barriers to the research, data, and innovations needed to address health crises, climate change, food insecurity, and education gaps” (UN, p.2). African Union frameworks likewise position STI centrally within [Agenda 2063](#).

Operational regional assets reinforce this alignment. The African Development Bank’s open-data portal provides a continent-wide platform for access and reuse, while AfCFTA offers institutional space for harmonised data governance and digital integration. The African Union Data Policy Framework highlights interoperability as an actionable lever, promoting an “integrated national data system” that enables cross-sector data flows and safe reuse, and recommending that “multi-sectoral open data initiatives should be implemented in priority data sectors like health, research and planning” (2022, p.52). Interviews suggest that **engaging finance and development planning ministries can extend leverage beyond science portfolios**.

Science diplomacy and multilateral arenas

Science diplomacy emerges across sources as a strategic arena for influence, particularly where formal enforcement is limited. **African engagement in multilateral negotiations** on climate, biosafety, AI, and health security creates openings to embed openness within global governance. STISA 2034 explicitly integrates “Science Diplomacy & Open Science” into its theory of change. This positions regional and multilateral forums as spaces to negotiate collaboration, infrastructure sharing, and benefit distribution.

The UN Scientific Advisory Board similarly notes that “Science can be a vital linchpin for effective decision making and action and has unique potential to foster international cooperation under even the harshest political conditions” (UN, 2025, p.1).

Incentives and research assessment as structural leverage

A recurring theme in interviews is that research assessment and funding conditions constitute the “hinge” of behavioural change. Publishing prestige and career incentives shape researcher choices, producing collective action dynamics: “Most of these issues are collective action problems... so people often look to funders, policymakers, and governments to change the incentives”. Universities also reinforce prestige publication incentives through hiring and promotion practices, particularly where global rankings shape institutional priorities. **Funding rules and assessment criteria are structurally influential levers**, with measures such as requiring the sharing of surveys, datasets, or tools in publicly funded projects identified as concrete and feasible entry points.

Connecting fragmented agendas

Several interviewees point to the alignment of Open Research with adjacent policy processes, such as research-for-impact frameworks, AI governance initiatives, and youth career development systems, highlighting its intersection with broader institutional reforms. In this view, **Open Research is not a standalone agenda but a cross-cutting governance issue**, requiring coordination across science, digital, education, and economic portfolios.

In summary, the strongest windows for systemic influence lie in formal institutional processes: reporting mechanisms, ministerial and parliamentary cycles, regional frameworks, science diplomacy, and reforms to funding and assessment rules. Multilateral norms matter, but leverage materialises when tied to mandates, budgets, legislation, and incentives. Across sources, there is convergence that institutional anchoring, not rhetorical endorsement, is decisive for advancing Open Research, even if actors differ on whether to prioritise legislative hooks, funding reforms, or regional coordination platforms.

4. Structural barriers to high-level prioritisation and system change

Barriers to Open Research reform are less technical than political and structural. Despite broad awareness of its benefits, **Open Research rarely secures sustained high-level prioritisation**. The main constraints lie in competing policy agendas, policy fragmentation, financing dependencies, regulatory complexity, entrenched incentive systems, and global asymmetries in publishing and infrastructure control.

Limited political salience and competing priorities

The first constraint is agenda competition. Although Open Research is rhetorically linked to development and digital transformation, it is rarely treated as a standalone political priority. Symbolic endorsement seldom translates into fiscal commitment or institutional reform. As noted, “The African Union [has] a history of policy documents that are not followed through due to member states’ lack of financial commitments” (Chiwere & Skelly, 2022, p.3). Boulton et al. similarly identify “Lack of understanding and commitment at political and policy levels” (2020, p.101) as a principal barrier. **The obstacle is weak political ownership and inconsistent follow-through.**

Policy fragmentation and coordination gaps

A further structural barrier is fragmentation across policies, infrastructures, and initiatives: “African science systems largely operate independently of each other, creating silos of incompatible policies, practices and data sets” (Chiwere & Skelly, 2022, p.3). Policy divides, across borders and across ministries, produce incompatible standards and undermine economies of scale. The African Union data policy framework identifies a “lack of general consensus on data governance frameworks” as a threat to interoperability, stressing that progress requires “leadership and political will for consensus” (2022, p.38). Fragmentation also interacts with financing constraints: **donor-driven initiatives may introduce parallel infrastructures or reporting requirements**, further reducing alignment with national systems.

Financing dependencies and donor influence

Financial constraints operate at both national and systemic levels. Many African STI systems face chronic **underinvestment and donor dependence**: “Overreliance on STI resourcing from external sources and distortion of common African priorities could imperil the realization of Africa’s Agenda 2063 aspirations” (STISA 2034, p.4). As one interviewee noted, “Obviously, limited funding is our key challenge here... our infrastructure is not quite enhanced”. Such dependencies curb reform ambition, as governments hesitate to commit to repositories, data infrastructure, or assessment reforms requiring sustained domestic financing.

Uneven digital infrastructure and human capacity compound the problem. Limited repository networks, weak persistent identifier systems, and unreliable connectivity create unequal participation across institutions and countries, making ambitious openness mandates politically and practically difficult to enforce. In many contexts, institutions also lack specialised roles such as data stewards, repository managers, and research software engineers needed to sustain Open Research infrastructures. Where such expertise is limited or concentrated in a few institutions, implementation remains uneven and often dependent on externally funded projects rather than embedded institutional capacity.

Regulatory complexity, AI governance, and sovereignty sensitivities

Legal and regulatory environments add further constraints. **Data protection regimes, cybersecurity concerns, and emerging AI regulations introduce caution and uncertainty.** While designed to safeguard rights and security, they can narrow the space for data sharing and cross-border collaboration. The African Union Data Policy Framework frames the dilemma as balancing “circulation of data to enhance value creation” (2022, p.9) with investment incentives and rights protections, calling for “positive enabling regulation” (2022, p.8) rather than a purely compliance-led approach. In practice, institutions often adopt risk-averse interpretations, slowing reform. Debates on openness also intersect with politically sensitive issues of data sovereignty and benefit-sharing. In African contexts shaped by histories of knowledge extraction, these concerns heighten scrutiny and complicate high-level prioritisation.

Publishing incentive structures

The most consistently cited barrier concerns academic and institutional incentive systems. Promotion criteria, grant eligibility, and international rankings continue to reward publication in high-impact journals rather than open practices: “Career-related concerns amongst researchers, who are currently motivated by incentives that are inimical to open science, remain a principal barrier” (Boulton et al, 2020, p.101). One interviewee noted that these dynamic shapes not only individual behaviour but institutional ambition: “Career progression and research assessment tend to privilege publication in high-impact journals. That shapes the entire system and narrows researchers’ ambitions, because it signals what is valued and what is rewarded”. **This incentive structure provides a political constraint on reform.** Universities and research elites may resist reforms that could weaken their positioning within global prestige rankings. Openness can therefore appear to threaten career mobility and institutional competitiveness.

Even where funders rhetorically endorse openness, grant design often remains output-focused: “Funders ask you for the final publication... but not for what is generated along the way”. Reporting systems continue to **privilege end products over open research processes**, weakening incentives to share intermediate outputs such as data, protocols, or tools, even as institutions increasingly balance openness with innovation and intellectual property considerations. The result is a systemic bias toward final publications. Valuable intermediate materials (datasets, code, survey instruments, methodological documentation) remain invisible and underused. Openness is thus narrowed to end products rather than embedded across full research cycles.

One interviewee highlighted emerging pressures within the publishing system linked to the rapid expansion of research outputs. As he noted, “particularly with AI, the rapid growth in the number of outputs is outstripping growth in funding,” contributing to a slowdown in the expansion of open access publishing. As publication volumes increase faster than the resources available to cover article processing charges (APCs), existing funding models struggle to keep pace.

Global market concentration and structural asymmetries

Global asymmetries in publishing and digital infrastructure constrain system-level change. **Commercial publishers and platform providers control the infrastructures that mediate research visibility and prestige.** As one interviewee noted: “The majority of publications originate in LMICs, yet they are often published through publishers based in high-income countries. That arrangement does not make much structural sense”.

This concentration of market power limits policy autonomy and makes reform contingent on negotiations with actors beyond national jurisdiction. Large commercial actors also negotiate national licensing or transformative agreements with governments and research consortia, reinforcing existing publishing models. Open Research reform thus intersects with global commercial structures that individual governments have limited capacity to influence.

In summary, these barriers indicate that the core constraint is political rather than technical. Open Research competes for attention within crowded policy agendas shaped by entrenched incentives, financing dependencies, regulatory complexity, fragmented governance, and global market asymmetries. These mutually reinforcing constraints limit prioritisation, weaken coordination, discourage institutional reform, and narrow room for manoeuvre—explaining why progress tends to be incremental rather than system-wide and transformative.

5. Framing and narrative competition in policy debates

How Open Research is framed shapes its political traction. Although normative support for openness is widespread, moral arguments alone rarely secure high-level commitment. Framing Open Research in terms of institutional priorities (economic growth, national development, integrity, sovereignty, or youth employment) may prove more effective in influencing policy agendas and funding decisions.

From moral imperative to instrumental justification

A recurrent theme across sources is that moral arguments alone are insufficient to drive change. There is a need to shift from framing openness as a moral obligation to presenting it as a strategic reform. As one interviewee explained: “At first, we approached it from a moral perspective... but that didn’t really lead to change. So, the framing shifted toward innovation, efficiency, and research integrity”. Another interviewee noted: “We have to align our arguments with national development plans to make it easier to convince governments to provide funding”. This instrumental turn does not abandon normative commitments; it reflects recognition that **decision-makers respond to frames aligned with budgetary, innovation, and governance priorities.**

Global public good and science diplomacy framing

A distinct but related narrative frames Open Research as a global public good essential to addressing transnational challenges such as pandemics, climate change, and AI governance. **Science is cast as a shared global resource** requiring cooperative stewardship rather than fragmented national control. In this framing, openness underpins international collaboration and trust amid geopolitical tension and commercial pressure. The political appeal lies less in strengthening multilateral legitimacy, collective problem-solving, and coordinated global governance. STISA 2034 translates this into an Africa-specific proposition by calling to “promote an African Open Science Platform” (p.17) and support implementation of open science practices across disciplines and communities of practice.

Public accountability and the “public funding” frame

Another influential narrative frames Open Research as a matter of public accountability. The claim that “Research produced with public funding should be publicly accessible” (interviewee) aligns with budget transparency and taxpayer rights and responsibility. It shifts the debate from abstract openness to fiscal fairness, particularly where public research funding is scarce and politically contested. Policy documents reinforce this logic, presenting how **openness can improve the efficiency and reliability of publicly funded research systems**. This framing may resonate with ministries focused on expenditure oversight and value for money.

Economic growth and return-on-investment narratives

Another influential frame centres on economic competitiveness and return on investment. As one interviewee argued, reform gains traction when it “tells a much more specific, detailed story about lost investment... about stagnation in economic growth... it needs to tell a very hard economic growth story”. **Articulating opportunity costs in economic terms** may persuade finance ministries more effectively than moral claims.

This framing aligns Open Research with innovation agendas, industrialisation strategies, and digital transformation plans. STISA 2034 links investment in open science to accelerating sustainable and inclusive industrialisation. The African Union’s Data Policy Framework similarly suggests that “The public sector can also create market value by opening certain data sets” (2022, p.8) and that “opportunities for entrepreneurial development and innovation may increase” (2022, p.14). Here, the emphasis shifts from access to value creation, jobs, and competitiveness. While this economic framing may enhance policy salience, particularly with finance and development ministries, there is caution that an exclusively growth-oriented narrative could sideline equity and public-good principles.

Research integrity, trust, and evidence-based governance

Open Research can also be framed as a mechanism to strengthen research integrity and public trust. By making research verifiable and open to scrutiny, open practices enhance reliability: “Open science (...) improves the quality, reproducibility and impact of science, and thereby the reliability of the evidence needed for robust decision making and policy and increased trust in science” (UNESCO, 2021, p.2). In policy environments concerned with misinformation, auditability, and evidence-based governance, this framing may resonate strongly. Here, **Open Research is positioned as a foundation for trustworthy public decision-making**.

Development, sovereignty, and epistemic rebalancing

In African and other Global South contexts, sovereignty and inclusive development narratives may be particularly salient. Open Research is framed not as passive access to global knowledge, but as a strategy to strengthen domestic systems and reclaim research value. Policy documents link openness to Agenda 2063’s ambition of building “a prosperous and integrated Africa”, while the SDG pledge to “leave no one behind” provides an equity lens: “SDGs big aspiration is leave no one behind... to inform more inclusive efforts you need evidence from all type of stakeholders” (interviewee). This framing connects openness to youth inclusion, gender equality, and national development priorities.

A related narrative highlights a **“gravity shift” in global knowledge production**, supporting Southern-led institutions to set partnership terms rather than comply with Northern mandates. **Open Research becomes a tool to rebalance epistemic power** and strengthen domestic agenda-setting. These themes are reinforced by African-centred ethical frames such as “Data Justice” and “Ubuntu,” which emphasise collective benefit and dignity. Openness is thus positioned as empowerment and fair benefit-sharing.

Audience-specific “sales pitches”

Interviews suggest framing is highly audience-dependent. As one interviewee summarised: “The framing depends on the audience: sometimes it’s about equity, sometimes about ownership and licensing, sometimes about reducing research waste or strengthening research integrity and collaboration”.

This highlights that Open Research does not travel through policy spaces as a single coherent message: equity narratives may resonate in development cooperation contexts; licensing and ownership arguments may appeal to sovereignty-sensitive actors; efficiency and waste-reduction frames can attract funders; and integrity frames gain traction among regulators and evidence-policy communities.

Youth employment emerges as a resonant entry point: “The argument that tends to resonate most is about young researchers: we are producing increasing numbers of researchers, but there are not enough clear career pathways for them. That issue seems to interest almost everyone”. This shifts the debate from abstract openness to labour markets, skills utilisation, and institutional sustainability, broadening engagement beyond science ministries to education and labour portfolios.

A further narrative targets market dysfunction in publishing: “Science has become over-commercialised. The market is dysfunctional and fails to deliver outcomes that serve society’s interests”. Here, Open Research is framed not simply as transparency reform, but as a corrective to structural imbalances in the knowledge economy, including the negotiating power of dominant publishing actors, an argument that may resonate with public funders concerned with value for money and regulatory oversight.

Counter-arguments and narrative resistance

While strategic framing can expand reform opportunities, interviews and documents also reveal persistent counter-narratives that constrain traction. These do not reject openness outright but foreground competing priorities and risk perceptions.

- **Research security and strategic sensitivity.** In contexts of geopolitical competition and dual-use concerns (e.g. AI, biotech), openness may be seen as exposing strategic assets. Security and digital governance actors can frame it as vulnerability rather than public good.
- **Sovereignty and unequal benefit sharing.** In African and Global South settings, openness can trigger concerns about data extraction by high-income country actors. As one interviewee stressed, it must rest on “a mutual understanding of benefit sharing”, or risk reinforcing asymmetries.
- **Commercial and institutional resistance.** Actors embedded in existing publishing and platform models may resist reforms that threaten revenue or prestige, invoking sustainability, quality control, or intellectual property protection.
- **Reform fatigue and incrementalism.** In systems already managing digital transformation, AI governance, and higher education reform, Open Research may be framed as an added burden rather than an enabling change.

In summary, the analysis underscores that framing is central to the political traction of Open Research. Instrumental (innovation, growth), accountability (“public funding/public access”), global public good, integrity, and sovereignty frames each mobilise different constituencies and policy arenas. In African contexts, development, inclusion, and a “gravity shift” toward Southern-led agenda setting are particularly resonant. Yet counter-narratives (around research security, unequal benefit-sharing, commercial interests, and reform fatigue) can temper ambition and slow uptake. Open Research thus advances within a contested discursive space, where framing shapes coalitions, policy alignment, and the scope of systemic change.

Five Priorities for Driving System Change

The analysis presented in the [previous section](#) shows that Open Research reform is not constrained by a lack of conceptual clarity or normative endorsement. Global and continental frameworks already legitimise openness. The central challenge is translating this legitimacy into institutional anchoring, incentive reform, and sustained political prioritisation. The Communiqué of the UN Conference Advisory Committee on Open Science stresses that advancing open science “requires not merely incremental adjustments but fundamental reform of how scientific knowledge is created, validated, shared, and incentivized” (2025, p.3). **Initiatives seeking to advance Open Research should therefore prioritise strategic influence over general awareness-raising**, with a deliberate focus on authority, incentives, and governance design.

Priority stakeholders and coalition-building

Institutional and policy entry points for influence

Incentives, infrastructure, and governance design

Strategic framing and political positioning

Learning questions for adaptive strategy

1. Priority stakeholders and coalition-building

Open Research reform advances when advocacy is attached to actors who control legislation, funding rules, and regulatory standards. Coalitions are necessary but insufficient unless linked to decision authority. Initiatives should prioritise institutional anchors and authority-linked coalition design.

Engage decision authorities first

Prioritise ministries responsible for science, innovation, ICT, data governance, and finance, alongside parliamentary committees and SGCs. Engagement should focus on rule-setting power: funding conditions, assessment frameworks, and regulatory updates. SGCs are strategic entry points, consistent with the SGCI phase three objective to strengthen their STI policy influence. Where possible, establish or participate in parliamentary Technical Working Groups or legislative advisory platforms to support drafting, amendment, and review processes. Moving from informal dialogue to structured engagement may increase the likelihood of formal adoption.

Anchor advocacy in continental commitments

Engage African Union Commission structures, AUDA-NEPAD, Regional Economic Communities (RECs), and sub-regional science bodies (e.g., EASTECO) by explicitly referencing STISA 2034 and African Union data policy instruments, which already recognise open science and interoperability. Frame advocacy as operationalising existing commitments rather than introducing new agendas. Complementary working groups at the level of RECs or African Union policy platforms could also help coordinate priorities and connect national reforms with regional agendas, supporting coordination and upward alignment.

Redesign coalitions around mandate and adoption

Structure coalitions with co-leadership from ministries or SGCs so that outputs (policy clauses, interoperability standards) can be formally adopted. Move from dialogue platforms to implementation platforms.

Link regional platforms to national reform

Use regional assets (e.g., regional data portals, RENS) to support national implementation. Position continental infrastructure as shared public goods that reduce duplication and build economies of scale. Developing regional research infrastructure roadmaps (such as South Africa's) could help prioritise investments and guide coordinated development of repositories, connectivity, and data infrastructures needed for Open Research ecosystems.

2. Institutional and policy entry points for influence

Open Research gains traction when embedded within structured policy processes rather than promoted as a standalone reform. The next phase should align advocacy with predictable institutional windows and broader reform agendas.

Leverage reporting and review cycles

Use UNESCO reporting obligations and African Union review processes as advocacy windows to introduce policy updates, legislative amendments, and funding rule adjustments. These moments can also be used to convene regional stakeholders (e.g., AUDA-NEPAD, national agencies, funders, and research institutions) to unpack the UNESCO Open Science Recommendation, translate it into regional and national priorities, and assess progress against shared benchmarks.

Embed openness in ongoing regulatory reform

Insert interoperability standards, trust mechanisms, and process-level transparency into AI governance, data protection reforms, digital transformation strategies, and STI strategy revisions. As AI-driven research expands, aligning openness principles with emerging AI governance frameworks will become increasingly important.

Position Open Research within industrial and development strategy

Use STISA 2034's explicit call to invest in open science under sustainable and inclusive industrialisation objectives to frame reform as economic transformation and innovation infrastructure.

Prioritise funding and assessment reform as entry points

Target grant conditions, reporting templates, and evaluation rubrics as immediate levers for behavioural change. Advocacy should focus on what changes researcher incentives, not only policy language. Initiatives such as SGCI can play a catalytic role by supporting cross-country funding calls that embed openness requirements and shared assessment criteria.

3. Incentives, infrastructure, and governance design

The primary structural barriers to Open Research are incentive misalignment, fragmented infrastructure, and governance uncertainty. System change requires institutional design reform, not only political endorsement.

Make research assessment reform a flagship workstream

Define and promote recognition of process outputs (datasets, protocols, implementation tools, engagement evidence) and open collaboration (community engagement, research user co-creation) in promotion, hiring and funding criteria across universities and funding agencies. Develop and provide ready-to-adopt institutional templates to reduce friction.

Institutionalise “process openness” through research funders

Encourage funders to think about lifecycle openness, considering both incentivising research user collaboration and requiring the sharing of intermediate research outputs, such as datasets, protocols, code, survey instruments, and implementation tools, generated during the research process, not only final publications. Structure incentives and expectations around collaboration and engagement within research funding frameworks. Develop an Open Process Outputs Standard requiring deposit and documentation of intermediate research outputs. Pair requirements with lightweight compliance tools and ethical guidance to ensure feasibility.

Promote a minimal interoperability package

Advocate for shared metadata standards, repository alignment, and persistent identifiers at the point of output creation. Prioritise standards over new platform creation to reduce fragmentation. Where absent, national research infrastructure roadmaps can help prioritise investments in repositories, connectivity, and data infrastructures for Open Research.

Strengthen trust mechanisms and enabling regulation

Support the development of clear rules for data use, responsibility, and liability to reduce institutional risk. Align with African Union emphasis on enabling regulation that builds capacity for safe reuse rather than imposing compliance-only mandates.

Promote differentiated implementation pathways

Avoid one-size-fits-all mandates and support tiered or modular adoption models that allow countries and institutions to align openness with capacity, risk tolerance, and development priorities. This reduces resistance and enhances political feasibility.

Strengthen professional capacity for Open Research infrastructures

Support the development of specialised institutional roles such as data stewards, repository managers, and research software engineers. Sustainable Open Research systems require dedicated technical and information management capacity within universities and research organisations, not only infrastructure investments.

4. Strategic framing and political positioning

Open Research rarely becomes a high-level political priority through moral arguments alone. Influence depends on aligning narratives with institutional incentives and demonstrating that reform is already operational and regionally grounded. African Union frameworks already recognise open science and open data principles; the advocacy task is to connect these commitments to visible national and regional practice.

Lead with public value and accountability

Frame reform around the principle that publicly funded knowledge should be publicly accessible. Provide policy toolkits (model clauses, cabinet memo language, phased implementation pathways) to facilitate adoption.

Use economic and industrial framing for high-level engagement

Position Open Research as enabling productivity, competitiveness, entrepreneurship, and digital economy participation, consistent with STISA 2034's industrialisation objectives. Link openness to innovation infrastructure and market creation.

Deploy audience-specific narrative matching

Use a deliberate narrative matrix:

- Finance ministries: return on investment and reduced waste
- Development and planning ministries: innovation and impact on national priorities
- Research funders: efficiency and impact
- Research institutions: research quality and competitiveness
- Researchers: visibility, collaboration, career pathways

Frame openness as sovereignty-compatible

Emphasise governed openness, trust mechanisms, and regional infrastructure to address extraction concerns. Position reform as strengthening domestic capability and agenda-setting power.

Map and showcase regional and national champions and flagship initiatives

Continuously identify, document, and communicate countries, institutions, and policy actors that are advancing Open Research across Africa. This should include flagship initiatives such as funding and assessment reforms, repository and interoperability systems, regional infrastructure platforms, and formal policy adoptions.

Develop concise, advocacy-ready case briefs that highlight the champion(s) involved, the reform achieved, the enabling conditions, and the tangible public value or efficiency gains observed. These examples should be used strategically in high-level engagement to demonstrate feasibility, reduce perceived risk, and reinforce that Open Research reform is already being led and implemented within African systems.

5. Learning questions for adaptive strategy

Because reform is political and context-dependent, future programmes and initiatives seeking to advance Open Research reform must adopt an adaptive approach informed by learning and engagement.

1. **Where is political appetite emerging?** Track where momentum is strongest in legislatures, executive ministries, funders, or regional bodies, and recalibrate engagement accordingly.
2. **Are incentive reforms operational or rhetorical?** Assess whether funding rules and assessment criteria are actually changing or remaining symbolic.
3. **Which coalition designs produce adoption?** Evaluate which configurations of authority-linked coalitions result in policy uptake rather than dialogue alone.
4. **Is Open Research embedded or siloed?** Monitor whether reform is being integrated into industrial, digital, and development strategies, or confined to science policy discourse.

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